

CURRENT FEATURES OF SOFT TISSUE CONTOURING IN THE AREA OF DENTAL IMPLANTS USING CAD/CAM TECHNOLOGY

(Literature review)

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ABSTRACT

A comprehensive digital protocol for dental rehabilitation with dental implants begins with data collection. This includes the results of 3D scanning and cone beam computed tomography (CBCT). Together, these allow proper planning of the implant procedure and further orthopaedic rehabilitation as a complete set of iatrogenic interventions. In this article, we will discuss the individual segments of a comprehensive digital dental rehabilitation protocol, concentrating more on the components of the prosthetic phase. Special attention will also be paid to the computer-aided design and computer-assisted manufacturing (CAD/CAM) phase.

Introduction. Nowadays, dental implantology makes it possible to increase significantly the efficiency of complex rehabilitation of patients with partial and total lack of teeth. In prosthetics on dental implants customised abutments are widely used as a supra-structure and have a number of advantages over standard abutments. During the design and milling of customised abutments, the anatomical shape and the relative parameters of the dental cervical region are taken into consideration separately for each dental segment in which the implant is placed. CAD/CAM technology is becoming increasingly popular in dentistry. In fact, this approach is an alternative and replacement for traditional methods of making dentures, including those supported by dental implants. There is

ample evidence that CAD/CAM has been shown to be clinically quite effective in cases of single crowns on implants (Pjetursson and colleagues, 2019), although the evidence for the feasibility of implementing CAD/CAM in different types of intraosseous titanium-supported dentures is much smaller and less conclusive. Research data show that the accuracy of implant-supported prostheses fabricated with CAD/CAM technology is at least comparable, and often better, than the results obtained with the traditional casting technique. The advantage of CAD/CAM is that this approach can also be used effectively for multi-modular (multi-component) prostheses and complete removable implant prostheses. 3D scanning can be performed using a laboratory or intra-oral scanner.

Photo 1. Intra-oral scan that can be used in the planning of the implant procedure according to the static navigation template. Intraoral scanning has a number of clinical advantages, including the ability to assess the quality of the obtained scan in real time (photo 1)

In addition, intra-oral scan data are compatible with clinical CAD/CAM machines and are also suitable for processing in specialised dental laboratories. In addition, this approach is also more hygienic with regard to the transmission of implant position data to the laboratory (photo 2,3).

Photo 2. Digital scanning is even more hygienic if there is a need for an impression during surgery. This approach is also

effective when the patient is undergoing orthodontic treatment.

Photo 3. The scan abutment incision in the coronal third of the construct is crucial for CAD/CAM modelling and determining the position of the implant. The scan abutment incision must be positioned so that it points in the vestibular direction and can be easily scanned during manipulation

However, so far there is no high level of evidence to justify the choice of digital scanning over analogue for dental implant impressions. The available literature, which shows the results of laboratory studies in greater numbers, demonstrates the high validity of intra-oral or laboratory impression techniques. Patients also report a higher level of acceptance of the procedure and satisfaction with the intraoral scan. Dentists should be aware that parameters such as the distance between implants (length of edentulous area), the depth of the intra-oral supports, the angle of their inclination, the experience of the dentist, the specifics of the various intra-oral scanning systems and even the scanning strategy itself, all affect the overall accuracy of the scans obtained. The overall aesthetic result is a decisive factor in a patient's emotional perception of the

effectiveness and success of the rehabilitation performed. Doctors need to remember that the aesthetics of the smile is a component of facial aesthetics. New technologies make it possible to capture the three-dimensional surface texture of the patient's soft tissues with laser and optical scanners. Currently, the only limiting factor in the formation of a fully virtual patient is the accuracy of the superimposition of the different data sets. For a more precise alignment, it is recommended to use the same anatomical landmarks as reference points on the intraoral, facial and CLCT scans. The future of virtual dental treatment planning is to be able to generate a 4D virtual patient with all dynamic movements and changes. Currently, none of the technologies on the market can fully account for all the nuances of dynamic changes in the dentition and soft tissues of the face. Most modern CAD/CAM systems are moving towards a so-called open architecture design. Open architecture allows the freedom to exchange digital data from 3D scans and between different types of software. Conversely, CAD/CAM systems with a closed architecture restrict the acquisition

of digital data and focus on the design and production of prostheses only within the boundaries of the same integrated system. The open architecture increases flexibility and allows the information to be integrated with the appropriate CAD software, thus extending the possibilities for the creation of a virtual dental patient. Another important advantage of the open architecture is the expanded possibilities for clinicians and dental technicians to access a wide range of manufacturing technologies and restorative materials without restriction (van Noort 2012). Digital information can be transferred between CAD programs and production platforms more efficiently if digital file formats are standardised and mutually consistent. There are over 140 different recognisable file formats, of which the most commonly used is the standard tessellation language (STL). However, the STL format is limited to the surface geometry of the 3D object without any representation of colour or texture (Grant and colleagues, 2016) (Photo 24-25). In cases where colour and texture parameters need to be preserved, file formats like OBJ (an open file format developed by Wavefront Technologies) or PLY (polygon file format or Stanford Triangle format) can be used (Davies and colleagues, 2017) (Photo 26). This is why OBJ or PLY files are used to transfer facial scan data, preserving 3D texture and colour information (Morton and colleagues, 2019). A closed CAD/CAM system can also use its own digital file format, which cannot be recognised by other types of software. Of course, options are now available to convert files of different formats, but this often involves loss of data. Although subtractive manufacturing has reached a high degree of efficiency, it is not without

disadvantages. The latter include consuming too much material, the impossibility of mass production and the fact that only one object can be produced in a single session. Additive manufacturing allows the creation of objects with small surface details (such as undercuts and cavities) and complex internal structures (van Noort 2012). Additive manufacturing is defined by the American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM) as "the process of joining materials to create objects from 3D model data, usually in layers, which fundamentally distinguishes it from subtractive manufacturing. The process is increasingly being used in dentistry to make three-dimensional objects out of polymers and metal alloys. According to ASTM, the types of additive manufacturing techniques are vat polymerisation, material extrusion, material sputtering, technology for melting material in a pre-formed layer and layer-by-layer electron-beam fusing of material. Although the vat polymerisation algorithm requires more extensive post-processing of the resulting object to remove unused material particles as well as additional polymerisation, this technology has become one of the most popular CAD/CAM manufacturing options in dentistry. Stereolithography (SLA) and direct light projection (DLP) techniques work according to this principle. Thanks to these methods, dental practices can now 'print' tooth models, surgical templates, custom trays, fixed and removable prosthetic constructions and occlusal splints. The widespread use of inexpensive desktop 3D printers has made it possible to increase the production of dental structures directly in the clinic setting, but such approaches to improving dental care in general have not

been sufficiently scientifically substantiated. Industrial 3D printers can use different production methods like inkjet printing, which allows different materials (in colour or hardness) to be worked on during the production of the same object (photo 38). For the fabrication of cobalt-chrome and titanium alloy frameworks, the method of melting the material in a pre-formed layer is quite effective (Katkar and colleagues, 2018). This is why in practice doctors are more inclined to use a mixed analogue-digital protocol during patient rehabilitation with fixed or removable structures supported by dental implants (Kachalia and colleagues, 2010). Partly unresolved are also the problems of recording dynamic changes and soft tissue movements in dentures that are also mucosa-supported. These nuances can also be solved by the combined use of

digital and analogue impressions. A great advantage of CAD/CAM modelling is the full visualisation of the contour of the future prosthesis and the accuracy of fabrication of the framework or the complete prosthetic restoration with subtractive or additive manufacturing techniques.

Conclusions: In individual clinical cases, therefore, clinicians and dental technicians may require analogue or 3D-printed patient models for the finishing of prosthetic constructions, clarifying their fit, application of veneering material and surface detailing. A partially digital rehabilitation protocol, although more time-consuming, offers unique opportunities to achieve proper functional and aesthetic results with dental implant-supported restorations

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